

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article presents innovative strategies that can improve the listening skills of secondary level students learning English language. Effective oral communication in English is a challenge for all ESL students at the secondary level, which in turn poses difficulties for English language teachers. The objective of this study was to assist both teachers and students in overcoming this issue by demonstrating the positive outcomes of implementing innovative strategies to enhance listening skills in English language.

Key words: strategies, comprehension, allure, language listening ability, obstacles, hinder.

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Introduction

Today, listening is one of the skills you use the most in your daily life. Listening is the foundation of your speaking, writing and reading skills. To practice listening, active listening is important, which means that you are actively paying attention to what you are listening to. Get used to listening to audiobooks, podcasts, news, songs, etc. and watch videos and movies in foreign languages. In this article, we'll look at the following listening strategies and how to use them: Once you've started listening regularly, your limited comprehension can still be frustrating. Here are some actions you can take.

- accept the fact that you don't understand everything.
- stay relaxed when you don't understand - even if you still struggle a bit to understand.
- do not translate into your mother tongue.
- listen to the essence (or general idea) of the conversation. Don't focus on the details until you understand the main idea.

Methodology

First, translation creates a barrier between the listener and the speaker. Second, most people keep repeating themselves. By staying calm, you can usually understand what the speaker is saying.

Translation creates a barrier between you and the speaker. When you listen to another person speak in a foreign language, the temptation is to immediately translate into your mother tongue. This temptation gets stronger when you hear a word you don't understand. This is natural because we want to understand everything that is said. But when you translate into your native language, you take your attention away from the speaker and focus on the translation process in your brain. It would be nice if you could put the speaker on hold. In real life, however, the person continues to speak while you translate. This situation

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probably leads to less - not more - understanding. Translation causes a mental block in your brain that sometimes prevents you from understanding anything. Think for a moment about your friends, family and colleagues. If they speak your native language, do they repeat the number themselves? If they are like most people, they probably do. That means that whenever you listen to someone speaking, it is very likely that they will repeat the information, giving you a second, third or even fourth chance to understand what has been said. By remaining calm, allowing yourself to not understand, and not translating while listening, your brain is free to concentrate on the most important thing: understanding English in English. Probably the greatest advantage of using the Internet to improve your listening skills is that you can choose what you would like to listen to and how many and times you would like to listen to it. By listening to something you enjoy, you are also likely to know a lot more of the vocabulary required. Use keywords or key phrases to help you understand the general idea. If you know "New York" and "business trip" and "last year"; You can imagine that people are talking about a business trip to New York last year. This may seem obvious to you, but remember that people are still talking. Imagine your English-speaking friend saying, "I bought these amazing artists from J.Band

I can barely listen to National Radio." If you don't know or understand what tuning is, you might be disappointed if you just focus on the word tuner. If you think about the context, it might make sense. for example; Shopping is pre-sale season, listening is no problem, radio delivers. Now you will understand. He bought something called a tuner to listen to the radio. The tuner must be of the radio type. This is a simple example, but it shows what you should focus on. It's not a word you don't know, it's a word you understand.

Discussion

Listening regularly is the most important way to improve your listening skills. Don't forget to relax and enjoy hearing what the Internet can do. Despite their importance in language learning, listening skills have long been relegated to a more general position in foreign language curricula.

With the advent of communicative language education and its emphasis on fluency, listening began to be taught and taught. However, listening has not been fully integrated into the curriculum and requires more time and effort. During class and homework. Listening to students is difficult for many reasons:

- Listening is different. Listening involves communication and interpretation. This requires the listener to have the opportunity to engage in a face-to-face conversation, or to not have the opportunity to hear what the other person is saying or going through.
- Listening includes all types of language. In addition to listening to lectures and presentations in academic and formal settings, students should participate in or listen to conversations involving different levels of spoken language.
- Listening involves "turning" and "decrease"; Language structure: In addition to working with words and language structure, listeners should learn to recognize language contractions (eg I want to go, wait for the minutes).
- There are different baud rates to listen to

Conclusion

Unlike a reading text that is at the learner's control, a listening text is constantly moving and at variable speeds that often cannot be controlled by the listener, because of all these factors, listening activities often create high levels of anxiety and stress among learners that can interfere with comprehension. For

teachers as well, addressing listening in the language classroom poses some challenges.

As a language teacher, one of your tasks will be to develop a vision of where listening fits within your teaching. As you progress through this module, continue to think of how you might plan to approach listening activities and what goals and expectations to set for your students

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